

D7.1 – TREX Branding and communication kit

Version 1.0

GA no 952165

Dissemination Level

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Translation
CMS	Content Management System
CORDIS	COmmunity Research and Development Information Service
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PC	Project Coordinator
PMB	Project Management Board
PPC	Pay-Per-Click
QMC	Quantum Monte Carlo
Q&A	Questions and Answers
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
R&D	Research and Development
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
UT	University of Twente

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1. Introduction

Every European Research and Innovation project faces formidable challenges when it comes to designing and executing an effective communication and dissemination strategy (Figure 1).

Figure 1 - Communication and dissemination strategy at glance

In delivering communication related to and on behalf of the TREX project, a keen eye has to be kept on the style of the communication, in order to keep consistency with the defined brand. The dissemination of TREX results is a crucial factor that is pursued through a number of communication and dissemination channels and tools aiming at informing and engaging the identified stakeholder communities about the project assets and results.

To this end, TREX will design, implement and constantly update a coordinated, efficient, and effective communication kit (*D7.1 TREX Branding and Communication Kit*, M2), as part of the more general *D7.3 TREX Communication, Dissemination and Stakeholders Engagement Strategy and Plan* (M6-M36). The Communication Kit will be a unique repository where all the general and specific information related to the project can be easily found.

This document is therefore intended to report about the *TREX Branding and Communication Kit*, one of the first online tools developed to pursue an optimal development of the TREX brand and visual identity, and to start spreading project recognition among relevant stakeholder groups while unifying the style of the communication revolving around the project.

While Chapter 1 of this document is intended to give a brief overview of the rationale behind adopting a communication kit inside a project like TREX, in Chapter 2, each section will present one of the items of the final Communication Kit, focusing on their specificities and features. Examples from the current version of the tool are provided in form of screenshots and references have been added for further information. The conclusions are drawn in Chapter 3.

2. The TREX Communication kit

The TREX Communication kit is a pre-packaged set of branding, promotional and informative materials gathered online at the address <https://trex-coe.eu/communication-kit>, that provides information about the project, to be distributed and used by partners and third-party stakeholders for communication and dissemination purposes.

Communication means promoting the project and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective manner and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other commercial players and policymakers, to contribute to the progress of science in general¹.

This deliverable reports on the initial set of communication materials that have been produced in the first two months of the project to define and promote TREX project's visual identity. It includes the project logo pack, social media accounts and graphical templates for the official documents. This material and the communication and dissemination items that will be produced in the upcoming months, will be collected and made available to partners and external users within the **TREX Communication Kit** section, in a dedicated page of the website².

At month 2, the TREX Communication kit (Figure 2) already includes a series of branding items, such as the logo and its variations, templates for internal and external communications, icons for social media use. In addition, one press release has already been produced and distributed³⁴.

Over the course of the project the Communication kit will evolve to cover the following, non-exclusive list:

1. Information on Open Access channels and visibility towards the EC dissemination channels
2. Social Media Channels & external communities links
3. Press releases & Press Clips
4. Collaterals: flyers, posters and one-pagers
5. TREX communication trends and web presence analytics
6. Official repository, including reference to licences, open access, Intellectual Properties sharing & patents

¹https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/dissemination-of-results_en.htm

²<https://trex-coe.eu/communication-kit>

³<https://www.hpccoe.eu/index.php/2020/10/22/providing-the-research-community-with-unique-exascale-computational-power-instruments-to-push-quantum-chemistry-simulations-a-step-further/>

⁴ <https://www.sissa.it/news/trex-new-european-centre-excellence-coe-sissa>

Communication Kit

TREX Communication Trends

Access this page to find information related to TREX website traffic and analytics and social media engagement.

Press Releases

21 October 2020: Providing the research community with unique exascale computational power instruments to push quantum chemistry simulations a step further

- [Read Online](#) - [Download](#)

TREX On The European Commission Platforms

The TREX project periodically publishes announcements on outcomes and results on the [Horizon CORDIS Platform](#):

- [Project Factsheet](#)
- [News & Multimedia](#)

TREX Logo Pack

A complete and comprehensive collection of all the project logo versions

Figure 2 - TREX Communication kit snapshot at month 2

2.1. TREX Branding - the logo pack

A meticulous process has been carried out in developing the most suitable visual identity of the project, taking into account the simplicity of its recognition and a good set of references to its main subject, while trying to keep an appealing look. Among the elements used in the logo design process (Figure 3) you can easily recognise a [Feynman diagram](#)⁵, a stack of elements (data, [quantum states](#)⁶), an atomic orbital (the [Rutherford-Bohr model](#)⁷ for the hydrogen atom). All the visual elements have been selected to recall, at glance, an adequate “look-and-feel” able to suggest the involvement of the project with the Quantum Chemistry domain.

⁵ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Feynman_diagram

⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Quantum_state

⁷ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bohr_model

Figure 3 - TREX logo definition over the time.

The logo has been refined over the time, and, once finalised, different variations have been designed, including a square version, a white version, and horizontal adaptations for social media (Figure 4, 6, 7). Banner images of the same style have been produced as well, to be used in general dissemination plan (Figure 5).

Figure 4 - Final TREX logo variations

Figure 5 - Branded, in-style image for general-purpose communication

Figure 6 - TREX LinkedIn header image and consortium page

Figure 7 - TREX Twitter profile page

2.2. TREX on the European Commission Open Access platforms

TREX has already identified a number of dissemination channels that will be exploited over the course of the project to highlight all the main assets and results. Announcements on the outcomes and results will be regularly published on the [Horizon CORDIS Platform](#)⁸, while the Key Exploitable Results will be published in the [Horizon Results Platform](#)⁹ in order to facilitate the project dissemination goals. These will be part of the Communication Kit for the sake of Open Accessibility of all TREX public documents and resources.

2.3. Social Media Channels

Social media enable the creation of dedicated channels engaging niche audiences. Discussions in specific topic groups, direct messaging, job positions advertising, and publishing relevant tagged posts, will contribute to build a loyal support base and the resonance of the project at the European level. Two branded social media platforms have been set up and populated: [Twitter](#)¹⁰ (@trex_eu) and [LinkedIn](#)¹¹. References to these two web pages, the project handle, and relevant hashtags, are part of the Communication Kit.

⁸ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/952165>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

¹⁰ https://twitter.com/trex_eu

¹¹ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/trex-eu>

2.4. Press releases and press clipping

Press releases will be regularly uploaded, so to ensure their indexability and grant their accessibility to any potentially interested media agency. To keep track of the mentions coming from all over the internet, press clippings will be collected via dedicated services like [Google Alerts¹²](#), and then made available via the Communication Kit.

2.5. Collaterals: Flyers, posters, and one-pagers

Dedicated collaterals such as flyers, posters, one-pagers, cards, etc. along with printable materials will be produced over the course of the project. The whole collection of these handouts will be published and made available for download inside the Communication Kit.

2.6. Working templates

To foster the TREX brand awareness both internally and on external channels, two Microsoft templates have been created, one for .ppt presentations and one for .doc documents. Both the templates follow the EC requirements for H2020 funded projects, indicating the EC logo and disclaimer.

All the partners have been warmly invited to fit their slides and pages inside these templates, so as to give visibility to the project and its brand when presenting TREX-related content during third party events. The templates are available on Microsoft Teams, the platform chosen for the consortium internal communication and file sharing, where privacy standards and integration with collaborative software (online word, excel and powerpoint) are granted. The TREX document templates will also be shared publicly in the Communication Kit for usage by third party stakeholders.

2.7. Analytics and Key Performance Indicators

To head towards impactful outputs, a set of measurable indicators on the communication performance has been put in place, enabling adoption of a data-driven communication strategy. These tools, woven into the dissemination strategy from its start, will support the communication strategy allowing a thorough fine tuning of our efforts in order to hit the KPI goals. So far monitoring has been activated for the website usage (Figure 10), Twitter (Figure 8) and LinkedIn engagement (Figure 9) and made available through an interactive monitoring dashboard made with [Google Data Studio¹³](#), making our data exploitable with ease.

¹² <https://www.google.com/alerts>

¹³ <https://datastudio.google.com/u/0/reporting/95322e86-ff02-414c-b3e9-0c41ae469a36/page/4mju>

Social Networks

Figure 8 - Snapshot of the TREX Twitter analytics section in the monitoring dashboard. Reference period 18/10 to 16/11 2020

Figure 9 - Snapshot of a TREX LinkedIn analytics section in the monitoring dashboard. Reference period 18/10 to 16/11 2020

Figure 10 - Snapshot of main TREX website analytics section in the monitoring dashboard. Reference period 18/10 to 16/11 2020

3. Conclusions

The Communication Kit is one of the key tools to ensure a coordinated and standardized communication among the TREX project stakeholders, for both internal and external communities alike. The kit is a live source that will be continuously updated during the entire project duration. All the sections and the items of this helpful tool have been described thoroughly in this document while a general structure of its final form has been depicted, tracing a path towards the development of more articulated and comprehensive Communication Plan, to be delivered in month 6 (*D7.3 Communication, Dissemination, & Stakeholders-Engagement Strategy and Plan*).

